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Chemical Investigation of the Roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*

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EARLIER communication¹ from this laboratory reported the isolation and characterization of two new glycoflavanones from the roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*. The plant is reputed for its medicinal importance.²

The air dried and powdered root of *P. niruri* was extracted with ethanol under reflux for 125 hr. The total ethanolic extract was kept in a refrigerator which deposited a white crystalline compound (0.92 g). Petroleum ether extract of the deposit gave a white amorphous mass (0.8 g) containing two compounds (TLC examination). These two compounds (designated as A and B) were separated over neutral alumina column, eluted with C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (6 : 4 v/v) and C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (2 : 8 v/v).

Compound-A, $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 211-12°, (α)_D²⁵ +27° (in $CHCl_3$) gave positive LB test for triterpenes. This was characterized as Lupa-20(29)-ene-3-β-01 by m.p., m.m.p., Co-IR and Co-TLC with an authentic sample of lupeol.

Compound-B, $C_{32}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 466), m.p. 213-14°, (α)_D²⁵ +50° (in $CHCl_3$) also gave a +Ve LB test for triterpenes. Alkaline hydrolysis of the compound-B gave an alcohol, identified as lupeol (Co-TLC and Co-IR)^{3,4} and CH_3COOH . Detailed study of the compound-B showed it to be the acetate of lupa-20(29)-ene-3-β-01 (confirmed by Co-TLC and Co-IR).

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Chemical Investigation of *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth (whole plant) and Leaves of *Ipomoea fistulosa* Mart

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IPOMOEA fistulosa Mart (Convolvulaceae) is a South American plant migrated to India. Prolonged ingestion of this plant results in wasting, depression and other ill-defined pathology in sheep, cattle and goats.¹ From the leaves of the plant previous worker² reported the isolation of some fatty acid glycosides. Our present communication reports the isolation of β-sitosterol from the leaves of the same plant.

Dried and powdered leaves of the plant were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) for 10 hrs. The crude residue on chromatographic separation over silica-gel yielded a white crystalline solid, m.p. 133-137°, which on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnished the corresponding acetate, m.p. 128-130° (Lit³ m.p. 127-128°), identical (m.m.p., T.L.C., and I.R.) with an authentic specimen of β-sitosteryl acetate. The benzene and ethylacetate extracts of the plant on chromatographic separation yielded no crystalline solid.

Gerbera lanuginosa Benth (Compositae) grows in the temperate Himalayas at the altitude of 4000-9500 ft. The white cotton like coating found under the surface of the leaves is used for straining wounds and is also used for making coarse cloth⁴. Since no chemical investigation on this plant has so far been reported we were interested to undertake a systematic chemical examination of the plant.

Dried and powdered whole plant of *G. lanuginosa* was successively extracted with (A) petroleum ether (60-80°) and (B) benzene. The petroleum ether